

A Probability Description of Two Body Scattering Momentum Conservation and the Position of the Interaction

Francesco R Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 12, 2024

In the case of two body scattering, collisions may occur at any x point with the same probability and momentum is conserved. It is possible to write the statement of momentum conservation as a probability: $P(p_3, p_4 \text{ final} | p_1, p_2 \text{ initial}) = 0$ if $p_1 + p_2 \neq p_3 + p_4$ and 1 otherwise. This gives the impression that there are two independent probabilities, i.e. $P(x)dx = dx/L$ for the position of the collision and the above for momentum conservation. To be complete, we argue that the two probabilities should be combined. This begs the question: Why does $P(x)dx = dx/L$ exist? We suggest that one may write $P(p)$ for each particle and that $P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_1 + p_2)$ suggesting a power law, i.e. $\exp(\text{constant } p)$. Given that this contains no x , it means the same probability holds for any x . $\exp(\text{constant } (p_1 + p_2))$ and $(\text{multiply with}) \exp(\text{constant } (p_3 + p_4))$ does not have any distinguishing characteristics associated with momentum conservation, i.e. $p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4$, and there is still the question of $P(x)dx = dx/L$.

We suggest that if one uses $-p_3 - p_4$ for the final momentum, then $\exp(-p_3 - p_4 + p_1 + p_2) = \exp(0)$. This result then matches $P(x) = 1/L$. Furthermore, one may introduce an x into $\exp(\text{constant } (-p_3 - p_4 + p_1 + p_2) x)$ because the momentum conservation condition creates a 0 which causes x to vanish as it should. If momentum is not conserved x does not vanish, but neither is probability 0. To make it 0, one is forced to consider lengths of with equally sized crests and troughs, i.e. change $\exp(px)$ to the complex periodic function $\exp(ipx)$. The lengths are linked to the p value, i.e. $\text{constant}/p$. As a result, the probability for non-conserved momentum is not 0 at each x , but only becomes 0 under integration over x . This suggests that physically one does not really have the notion of resolution of each x , but rather that there is a resolution of \hbar/p . This statement is born out experimentally by the existence of 2-slit interference etc.

This probability picture implies that a single particle is described by $\exp(ipx)$, (we set $\text{constant} = 1$) which means that there is discreteness in space, yet there is still a velocity. One cannot define it by dx/dt if dx and dt are smaller than dx and dt resolution lengths. (Note: one may introduce $\exp(iEt)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$ to create a probability which allows for energy conservation with the collision occurring at any time.) Thus, x and t are independent and range over space and time, but E and p necessarily define a classical velocity which cannot disappear from the probability scenario. The probability picture contains E, p, x, t as variables in the probability. From special relativity, if p changes and m_0 is held constant, the change is proportional to dv , while a change in dE (m_0 constant) is proportional to $v dv$. Thus, one might ask: How should x and t change to accommodate a change in p with m_0 (rest mass) held constant? Requiring x, t to change to offset dp , $dE, dm_0 = 0$ is equivalent to $dP/dp = 0$ (m_0 constant). This requirement also yields the probability $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. We discuss why conservation of energy and momentum should be inherent in $P(p, E, x, t)$ obtained solely through the $dP/dp = 0$ consideration, $m_0 = \text{constant}$.

The Form $P(x)dx = dx/L$

Formally in the literature (1), $P(x)dx = C/v(x) dx$ where $v(x)$ is velocity defined by $.5mv(x)v(x)+V(x) = E$. If $V(x)=0$, then $v(x)=\text{constant}$ and:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad ((1)) \quad \text{Here } L \text{ is length.}$$

((1)) is a uniform distribution, however, and in principle has nothing to do with dynamics. It is simply a description of an event occurring at different x values. We suggest that such an event may be the scattering of two particles. Such scattering conserves momentum in classical physics and it is possible to write momentum conservation in terms of probability, i.e.

$$P(x, (p_3, p_4 \text{ final}) (p_1, p_2 \text{ initial})) = 0 \text{ at any } x \text{ if } p_1 + p_2 \neq p_3 + p_4 \text{ and } 1 \text{ otherwise} \quad ((2))$$

To be complete, x should be part of the probability statement. Thus, ((2)) is the probability statement wanted, but what about ((1))?

If one considers a probability for a single particle, $P(p_1)$, then

$$P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_1 + p_2) \text{ (one dimensional arguments)} \quad \text{so } P(p_1) = \exp(\text{constant } p) \quad ((3))$$

If this is the case, then there is nothing distinguishing:

$$\exp(\text{constant } (p_1 + p_2 + p_3 + p_4)) \quad ((4))$$

In the case of momentum conservation versus non-conservation.

Furthermore, ((4)) is not at all linked with ((1)). We suggest, however, that there is a way to link ((4)) and ((1)) and bring in the notion of the reaction occurring at any x with the same probability and that is to use $-p_3 - p_4$ for the final momenta. Then ((4)) becomes:

$$\exp(\text{constant } (p_1 + p_2 - p_3 - p_4)) = \exp(\text{constant } 0) = 1 \quad ((5))$$

In such a case, one may introduce x , because it appears in ((2)) and it disappears if momentum is conserved meaning that any x value has the same weight. Thus:

$$P(p) = \exp(p x) \text{ where constant is set to } 1 \quad ((6))$$

There are two problems with ((6)). First probability increases indefinitely with x and secondly, one does not obtain the $=0$ part of ((2)). In fact, if momenta are not equal, then x need not disappear because such a reaction cannot occur. Thus, by inserting i in $\exp(px)$ to create $\exp(ipx)$ one solves both problems. The consequence, however, is that there is a discrete length, $\text{constant}/p$ (where the constant is \hbar -not proved here) associated with a single particle. This is irrelevant to two body scattering because with the $-p_3 - p_4$ formalism, momenta in ((5)) add to 0 and x disappears. There are, however, physical consequences of having a length associated with $\exp(ipx)$ such as 2-slit interference etc. Furthermore, there are consequences

on velocity. In other words, non-momentum conservation demonstrates that this condition does not hold at each x point (like momentum conservation does). One only has \hbar/p resolution in x , which is a strong physical statement, but is nevertheless born out experimentally. This means that the statement of conservation of momentum at each x , i.e. the notion of infinite resolution is really an idealization. Thus, Newtonian mechanics, which only deals with momentum conservation (for two body scattering) does not notice that there is resolution in space (\hbar/p) because the non-conservation situation is not considered (in the two body scattering problem).

$\exp(ipx)$ and Consequences on Velocity

We argued above that $P(x)dx = dx/L$ applies to conservation of momentum in two body scattering at any x point. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ describing a single particle with momentum p . In other words there is chunkiness in x , i.e. \hbar/p .

The same arguments that lead to $\exp(ipx)$ may yield $\exp(iEt)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$ for conservation of energy of two particles at any time. A possible issue is that given E and p (and hence $v = p/E$ from special relativity) ($c=1$), then how does one deal with $v = dx/dt$ from Newtonian mechanics and \hbar/E and \hbar/p time and length chunks? We argue that $v = x/t$ with x and t starting at 0 and measured using the chunks \hbar/E and \hbar/p .

One may note from special relativity that holding m_0 constant means dp goes as dv while dE goes as $v dv$. Here $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $c=1$. A change in dp with m_0 constant means that dE shows the original v value. One may suggest that x and t change to offset the change in dp , dE (m_0 constant). In other words:

$$dP/dp \text{ holding } m_0 \text{ constant} = 0 \text{ with } x \text{ and } t \text{ adjusting to allow for this } ((7))$$

$$\text{As shown in a previous note: } dP/dp = 0 = dP/dp \text{ partial} + dP/dE \text{ partial } v \text{ (} m_0 \text{ constant)}$$

$$\text{If } dP/dp \text{ partial} = x \text{ and } dP/dE \text{ partial} = -t, \text{ one has a solution, i.e. } P = \exp(-iEt + ipx) \text{ } ((8))$$

This approach actually yields the sign of E , i.e. $\exp(-iEt)$. The question becomes: Where is conservation of energy and momentum in this scheme?

Given the linear condition: $-vt + x = 0$ and $v = dE/dp$ with m_0 constant, one may essentially create a frequency for $\exp(-iEt)$ and one for $\exp(ipx)$. These functions are orthogonal with $\exp(-iE_2t)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$ and this leads to separate conservation laws. Thus, the linearity of $x - vt$ together with a probability which neither grows or shrinks indefinitely in x, t leads to an argument of the probability which is linear in Et and xp and allows for a derivative to be 0 if x and t adjust in a certain way, but at the same allows for orthogonal functions which imply conservation of E and p .

Conclusion

In general, in the literature $P(x)dx = dx/L$, is applied to a particle moving with constant velocity (1). We suggest that the uniform distribution is better applied to positions of two body scattering interactions. At the same time, momentum must be conserved so we seek a more general $P(x, (p_3, p_4 \text{ final}) (p_1, p_2 \text{ initial}))$. Why should this probability differ from $P(x)dx = dx/L$? We argue that $P(p_1)P(p_2)=P(p_1+p_2)$ (one dimension). Thus $P(x, (p_3, p_4 \text{ final}) (p_1, p_2 \text{ initial})) = \exp(\text{constant} (p_1+p_2+p_3+p_4))$. This, however, does not distinguish a conserved momentum situation from a non-conserved one and x does not appear even if momentum is not conserved. We suggest that using $-p_3-p_4$ solves the problem because one may write: $\exp(x p)$ (with constant=1). Then $P(x, (p_3, p_4 \text{ final}) (p_1, p_2 \text{ initial})) = \exp(0 x)$ for conserved momentum and x disappears showing equal probability for any x . $\exp(0x)$ is the same as $1/L$ from the uniform distribution.

The problem is what does one do for the case where p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 do not lead to momentum conservation? X need not disappear in such a case and introducing i , i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ leads to a non-indefinitely growing probability and also conservation of momentum, albeit in a length of space.

Furthermore, $\exp(ipx)$ suggests a chunkiness in space given by \hbar/p . The above arguments may be repeated for E, t leading to chunkiness in space. This leads to issues with $v=dx/dt$. We suggest using x/t ($x=0$ when $t=0$) and measurements of x and t respect the chunkiness/resolution). It is possible to find $P(E, p, x, t)$ by using $dP/dp=0$ for $m_0=0$ with x and t adjusting to offset a change dp which is proportional to dv while dE is proportional to $v dv$ from special relativity ($m_0=\text{constant}$).

References

1. Majernick, V. and Ophthalmy, T. Entropic Uncertainty Relations For a Quantum Oscillato
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231048623_Entropic_uncertainty_relations_for_a_quantum_oscillator
January 1999 Journal of Physics A Mathematical and General 29(9):2187
January 1999 29(9):2187 DOI:[10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029](https://doi.org/10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029)